

A Strategy for Enhancing Privacy and Usability of Crowdsourced Data

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Abstract—Crowdsourced data collection in citizen science experiments offers valuable insights but also raises significant privacy and usability challenges. When contributors collect data using personal devices, without adhering to strict data collection guidelines, the resulting geolocated data may reveal sensitive information, such as home or workplace locations and mobility patterns. At the same time, uneven spatial coverage in the collected data can lead to an unbalanced distribution, reducing its broader analytical value. This study explores strategies to enhance both privacy and usability of already collected crowdsourced data by refining data processing methods. By addressing issues related to spatial density, movement patterns, indoor/outdoor classification, and geographic contextualization, the aim is to improve the balance between protecting user privacy and preserving the integrity of crowdsourced datasets for scientific research.

Keywords—crowdsourcing, citizen science, privacy protection, data anonymization, spatial analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

The limited spatial coverage of existing authoritative observational networks and surveying campaigns makes it difficult to capture a comprehensive picture of processes and environmental conditions within a city [1]. The issue lies in the lack of data granularity needed to reflect dynamic, localized changes, particularly in rapidly evolving urban environments. To address this gap, crowdsourced data collection practices are gaining increasing popularity and broader adoption [2], [3], [4]. By leveraging the widespread use of digital technology, such as mobile apps, wearable devices, and IoT sensors, these practices make real-time, high-resolution data capture across an extensive area more easier than ever before. This is especially valuable in regions where conventional observations are sparse or entirely absent, providing critical data that would otherwise be difficult to obtain.

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It is equally well-known that there are challenges associated with the data obtained through crowdsourcing [2], [5]. Specifically, issues such as data quality and consistency are quite common, often arising from improper sensor use, incorrect sensor positioning, or sporadic sensor failures that go unnoticed until the data is post-processed. However, what is even more concerning is the unintentional collection of sensitive personal information, attributed to a lack of clear guidance on how to properly set up and use the sensors. This can lead to the inadvertent capture of private data, such as home or workplace locations, mobility patterns, and other sensitive details. Ultimately, all this sensitive information must be later discarded, resulting in a significantly reduced pool of usable data.

To tackle these challenges, this study builds on insights from an ongoing EU Innovation Action GREENGAGE funded under the Horizon Europe framework [6]. The GREENGAGE project harnesses active citizen participation in data collection by equipping individuals with portable digital devices, enabling them to capture data from their surrounding environments and contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of local conditions and processes. Since these participants are predominantly non-experts with little to no prior experience in data collection, it is reasonable to anticipate issues related to data quality, consistency, and reliability. Without the necessary experience or training, participants may encounter difficulties in effectively handling the devices, which can lead to inconsistencies in the collected data [7]. In this context, the contribution focuses on developing post-processing strategies to enhance the privacy and usability of crowdsourced datasets.

The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- **Computational method for detecting sensitive information in crowdsourced data:** An algorithmic approach to identify sensitive data points in crowdsourced data during post-processing, while ensuring that enough valuable

information remains for a robust analysis.

- **Strategy for enriching crowdsourced data:** An algorithmic approach to enrich the crowdsourced dataset with semantic information, adding descriptive, contextual, and relational attributes to raw data points.

This paper is organized as follows: Section II introduces the project-specific digital devices used for data collection, along with the challenges in user-driven data collection and associated data considerations. Section III outlines strategies for data enrichment and privacy enhancement. Section IV provides a critical discussion of the results and their implications. Finally, Section V concludes with a summary of the main contributions.

II. CHALLENGES AND CONSIDERATIONS IN USER-DRIVEN DATA COLLECTION

A. User-driven Operation of Portable Sensor Devices

As mentioned at the outset, participants in the GREEN-GAGE data collection campaigns are equipped with specialized portable digital devices. One such device is the Atmotube PRO, a portable air quality monitoring device that records environmental parameters such as particulate matter (PM1, PM2.5, PM10), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), temperature, humidity, and atmospheric pressure [8]. The Atmotube PRO was proven to have acceptable measurement accuracy especially for PM1 and PM2.5 [9]. The device continuously logs geolocated data at regular intervals. However, since its operation depends entirely on users choosing to power it on, its operation often occurs outside structured scientific campaigns, leading to unintended data collection. This continuous recording approach creates a rich but analytically complex dataset where measurements are driven by individual user behavior rather than systematic sampling protocols.

B. Challenges and Implications of Unstructured Data Collection

Unlike controlled environmental monitoring campaigns, where data is collected systematically across predefined locations and timeframes (e.g., using authoritative, stationary air quality stations), uncontrolled portable sensor data collection reflects individual usage habits. This can lead to high-density recording at static locations, such as homes, offices, or frequently visited places, resulting in overrepresentation of specific microenvironments. When these microenvironments are predominately indoor spaces, the collected data reflects unique air quality conditions influenced by factors such as HVAC systems, indoor activities, and building materials, which may differ substantially from concurrent outdoor conditions [10]. This overrepresentation can skew the dataset, making it less representative of broader environmental conditions and reducing its comparative value for regional air quality analysis. This equally leads to the resulting data patterns reflecting users' daily routines and device usage habits, rather than capturing the target data accurately. This poses dual challenges.

From a *privacy perspective*, the continuous recording of geolocated measurements can reveal sensitive information

about users' daily patterns and frequently visited locations. Since the device records and transmits geolocated data, prolonged use in fixed locations creates identifiable patterns, further increasing the risk of exposing the location of users' private spaces. Additionally, mobility patterns, such as daily commutes and frequently visited locations, can be inferred from the dataset, further aggravating privacy risks. Essentially, the resulting high-density clusters of geotagged measurements can effectively pinpoint residential addresses, workplaces, and routine movement behaviors, raising ethical concerns regarding participant anonymity.

From a *usability perspective*, the unstructured nature of data collection results in an uneven distribution of measurements across different scales - from broad geographic regions and cities down to specific environmental contexts (such as indoor versus outdoor locations), potentially limiting the dataset's applicability for systematic environmental analysis.

C. Opportunities in Data Processing

While the unstructured nature of data collection presents challenges, the rich geolocation data can be leveraged to enhance both privacy protection and research value through careful post-processing. By analyzing data patterns, it is possible to identify and flag different types of measurements based on their characteristics. For example, high-density record clusters at fixed locations can indicate potentially sensitive areas, while data points collected during high-speed movement can indicate transit-related measurements. Additionally, leveraging building footprint data from OpenStreetMap [11] allows for precise determination of which measurements were collected inside buildings, providing a direct method to differentiate between indoor and outdoor air quality readings.

These identified patterns, though privacy-sensitive in their raw form, can be transformed into valuable research insights. By combining building boundary detection with spatial density analysis and enriching the georeferenced data with administrative region information (such as municipality or district boundaries), meaningful large-scale comparative studies can be enabled while effectively protecting individual privacy. This approach allows for aggregation and analysis of air quality patterns at various administrative levels and environmental contexts (i.e., indoor/outdoor) without exposing specific locations or individual movement patterns.

The following section details our implementation of these enrichment strategies, demonstrating how multiple analytical approaches can work together to balance data utility and privacy protection in crowdsourced environmental monitoring.

III. STRATEGIES FOR DATA ENRICHMENT AND PRIVACY ENHANCEMENT

In this section, an integrated approach to enhancing privacy and usability of crowdsourced data collected via Atmotube PRO devices is explored. The methodology focuses on enriching the dataset with additional contextual information that enables privacy-preserving measures while maintaining analytical value. The goal is to balance the need for detailed

environmental data with the imperative of protecting user privacy, especially when the dataset might be made publicly available.

Implementation Technology: The entire data processing framework was implemented in Python, utilizing specialized libraries for geospatial analysis and data processing: GeoPandas and Shapely for geometric operations and spatial data handling; Pandas and NumPy for efficient data manipulation and numerical computation; rtree for spatial indexing to optimize geographic queries; and OSMnx for retrieving building footprint data from OpenStreetMap.

The proposed framework combines multiple analytical approaches to process the crowdsourced data in a privacy-conscious manner:

- 1) **Spatial Density Analysis:** The spatial distribution of data points is analyzed to identify high-density collection areas, which may indicate privacy-sensitive locations.
- 2) **Building Boundary Detection for Indoor/Outdoor Classification:** Building footprint data from the OpenStreetMap (OSM) is used to distinguish between indoor and outdoor measurements.
- 3) **Mobility Pattern Recognition:** Movement speeds are analyzed by comparing the relative distance between data points and their time signatures, to differentiate between stationary and in-motion measurements.
- 4) **Geographic Contextualization:** The data is enriched with geographic information on administrative boundaries to enable regional analysis while protecting privacy by avoiding the exposure of precise locations.

These components work together to create a dataset that supports flexible privacy-utility trade-offs for different research applications.

A. Identification of High-Density Collection Areas

The first component of the framework focuses on analyzing the spatial distribution of data points to identify potentially privacy-sensitive locations. This analysis employs efficient computation through vectorized operations to process large quantities of geospatial data. High-density areas often correspond to places where users spend significant time, such as homes or workplaces. A grid-based approach was employed to identify these areas:

- 1) **Grid Creation:** A grid is overlaid on the geographic area of interest, with each cell representing a fixed area (e.g., 50x50 meters).
- 2) **Density Calculation:** For each grid cell, the number of data points that fall within its boundaries is counted.
- 3) **Identification of Hotspots:** High-density areas are identified by selecting grid cells with point counts significantly higher than the average, specifically labeling cells where the count exceeds the mean plus 3σ (standard deviations).
- 4) **Optimization of Hotspot Locations:** Hotspot identification is refined by analyzing the data in more detail

Fig. 1. Spatial density grid analysis example, with high-density areas ($> 3\sigma$) clearly visible. Datapoints falling within the high-density areas are flagged as privacy-sensitive.

across four cardinal (north, south, east, west) and four intercardinal directions (northeast, northwest, southeast, southwest) to determine the exact location where the highest density of data points occurs.

See Fig 1. for exemplary result of this analysis.

Critical Considerations: This analysis depends significantly on data quality and distribution patterns. The initial analysis of crowdsourced air quality monitoring datasets revealed highly skewed distributions of spatial point density. This characteristic of the data motivated the adoption of a 3σ threshold approach, as it effectively handles non-normal distributions while maintaining sensitivity to extreme values. In a representative example, the analysis revealed a mean of 107 points per cell with a standard deviation of 4,585, resulting in only 0.07% of cells (3 out of 4,580) exceeding the 3σ threshold. In highly right-skewed distributions typical of human mobility patterns, the extreme threshold effectively isolates only the most frequently visited locations—exactly the privacy-sensitive areas to be identified. It’s important to note that without contextual information, high-density locations may be misinterpreted. What appears to be a privacy-sensitive location might actually be a sensor deliberately placed outdoors for extended monitoring.

B. Building Boundary Detection for Indoor/Outdoor Classification

The second component of the framework focuses on using building footprint data from OpenStreetMap (OSM) to classify measurements as indoor or outdoor. This classification is critical for both privacy protection and data interpretation,

as indoor environments can reveal sensitive locations while exhibiting distinct air quality patterns. The building detection approach consists of two main phases:

- 1) **Building Data Processing:** A bounding box that encompasses all GPS points is calculated and building footprints are fetched from OpenStreetMap within this area.
- 2) **Spatial Analysis:** Measurements falling within building boundaries are efficiently determined:
 - a) A spatial R-tree [12] index is created on building polygons to optimize spatial queries.
 - b) Measurement points are converted to a geospatial format compatible with the building polygons.
 - c) A two-stage spatial join is performed - first using the spatial index to identify candidate buildings, then conducting precise geometric containment tests.
 - d) Each measurement is labeled with a binary indoor/outdoor classification based on this analysis.

This approach yields a critical new dimension for data interpretation: the ability to differentiate between indoor and outdoor measurements. Indoor data points often represent private spaces such as homes or workplaces, making them particularly sensitive from a privacy perspective. Additionally, indoor environments typically exhibit distinct air quality patterns due to different sources of pollution, ventilation characteristics, and occupant activities. Fig. 2 presents the result of this analysis performed on a sample dataset.

The computational efficiency of building boundary detection is critical when processing large urban datasets. Our implementation addresses this challenge by employing spatial indexing through R-tree structures, which reduce the computational complexity of point-in-polygon operations from $O(n \times m)$ to $O(n \times \log(m))$, where n is the number of data points and m is the number of buildings. Testing with a dataset of approximately 500 thousand points and 1.35 million building polygons, the processing time was reduced to under 5 minutes. For further performance optimization distributed processing could be implemented as the geographical space of interest can be partitioned and processed in parallel.

Critical Considerations: The accuracy of this classification depends significantly on the completeness and precision of OpenStreetMap building data, which varies considerably across different regions. Urban areas typically have comprehensive building coverage, while rural or developing regions may have significant gaps. Additionally, the geometric precision of building outlines can vary based on the methods used for their creation in OSM. Finally, GPS accuracy, particularly in urban canyons or indoor spaces, can cause measurements to be incorrectly classified if location errors place them inside or outside buildings incorrectly.

Nevertheless, when combined with density analysis and movement pattern recognition, building detection provides a powerful tool for both enhancing privacy protection and improving analytical capabilities. Researchers can selectively

Fig. 2. Representative results from the building boundary detection phase, with individual data points classified as indoor (red) and outdoor (blue).

exclude indoor measurements to protect privacy while focusing analysis on public outdoor spaces, or they can separately analyze indoor and outdoor environments to better understand distinct pollution patterns.

C. Movement Pattern Recognition Through Speed Analysis

The analysis continues by examining the movement patterns between consecutive measurements. This analysis helps distinguish between stationary and in-transit measurements, providing valuable context for both privacy protection and air quality interpretation. The processing workflow involves calculating new metrics for distance, time, and speed from the original measurement data. Additionally, data points were classified as stationary, active movement (walking, biking), or in transit based on the calculated speed at each timestamp. The speed-based analysis followed these steps:

- 1) **Time and Distance Calculation:** For each pair of consecutive data points, the time difference is calculated based on timestamps and the linear geographic distance between them.
- 2) **Speed Calculation:** Movement speeds are calculated by dividing the distance between consecutive data points (prior and next) by the time difference, resulting in measurements in kilometers per hour (km/h).
- 3) **Mobility Classification:** Based on calculated speeds, data points are classified into mobility categories (e.g., stationary, active movement, transit) to provide context for environmental measurements.
- 4) **Classification refinement:** The categories were then refined within a 5min time frame to account for short pauses in trips or erroneous location data points.

Fig. 3. Representative results from the speed-based movement pattern recognition phase, with individual data points classified as active mobility (yellow), stationary (blue), and in transit (green).

The speed-based analysis not only aids in protecting user privacy by identifying potentially sensitive movement patterns but also enhances the dataset’s usability by providing context for the conditions under which data was collected. By distinguishing between stationary and transit data, more accurate and meaningful environmental analyses can be enabled. See Fig 3. for a representative result of this analysis performed on a sample dataset.

Critical Considerations: Speed calculation relies heavily on the accuracy of location data from users’ smartphones, which varies based on device quality and location services settings. This dependency can lead to inaccuracies in speed calculation and subsequent mobility classification.

D. Geographic Enrichment for Privacy-Preserving Analysis

The final component of the framework enriches the dataset with administrative boundary information to enable robust and meaningful analysis while protecting individual privacy:

- 1) **Boundary Data Integration:** Administrative boundary data (municipalities, provinces) are acquired and a spatial index is created to optimize spatial operations.
- 2) **Spatial Join Processing:** Measurement points are converted into a geospatial format and a spatial join is performed with administrative boundaries using an R-tree index to efficiently match points to polygons.
- 3) **Data Aggregation Options:** The enriched dataset supports multiple levels of aggregation (neighborhood, municipality, province), offering flexible privacy-utility trade-offs.

This geographic enrichment process adds valuable context while supporting privacy preservation through location generalization. By enabling analysis at various administrative levels, researchers can study regional patterns without accessing specific locations or individual movement data. See Fig 4. for a representative result of this analysis performed on a sample dataset.

Critical Considerations: The effectiveness of geographic enrichment depends on the quality, currency, and resolution of the administrative boundary data, which varies significantly across different regions. Administrative units also differ greatly in size and population density, creating inconsistent privacy protection levels (e.g., smaller municipalities provide less anonymization than larger ones). Additionally, measurements near boundary edges may create interpretation challenges when aggregated.

E. Final Dataset Structure

The final result of the processing framework is an enriched dataset that maintains all original measurement data while adding enrichment attributes for privacy protection and contextual interpretation:

- **Mobility metrics:** distance from previous point, time elapsed since previous measurement, and calculated travel speed
- **Mobility classification:** categorization as stationary, active movement, or transit
- **Privacy indicators:** binary flags for potentially privacy sensitive locations and indoor/outdoor classification
- **Administrative context:** municipality and region information for geographic aggregation

Fig. 4. Choropleth map showing the distribution of measurements across municipalities. Color intensity indicates total number of measurements.

TABLE I
DATASET CHARACTERISTICS BY LOCATION

Characteristic	Copenhagen	Rome	Gerace	Turano
Total Points	4,678	42,135	13,070	192,532
Indoor Points (%)	60.80	44.14	56.04	1.75
High Density Points (%)	68.04	72.44	78.96	89.30
Stationary (%)	96.39	95.30	89.47	97.90
Active Movement (%)	0.43	1.97	4.12	0.24
Transit (%)	3.19	2.72	6.40	1.86

These enrichment attributes maintain the full analytical value of the original air quality measurements while enabling researchers to selectively filter or aggregate data based on specific privacy requirements and analytical needs. Rather than permanently transforming or removing data, this approach offers maximum flexibility by providing the metadata necessary to create privacy-preserving views of the dataset for different applications.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Overview of Crowdsourced Data Characteristics

In this section, the characteristics and distribution patterns of Atmotube PRO data collected across four contrasting geographic locations: Copenhagen (Denmark), Rome, Gerace, and Turano (Italy) are analyzed. After application of the privacy-preserving enrichment framework, an examination is made of how the resulting datasets differ in terms of spatial coverage, indoor/outdoor distribution, mobility patterns, and privacy-sensitive concentrations. By comparing these distinct datasets, it is possible to evaluate how the framework performs across diverse collection patterns and environmental contexts.

Table I summarizes the key characteristics of each dataset, highlighting the differences in measurement distribution, movement patterns, and spatial contexts.

Table I reveals significant variations in data characteristics across the four geographic locations, highlighting both methodological considerations and privacy implications. The most striking variation appears in the indoor classification results, with measurements categorized as indoor ranging from 60.80% in Copenhagen to only 1.75% in Turano. This extreme disparity is unlikely to reflect actual usage patterns in these two usage instances but instead results from two technical factors. The primary factor is the uneven quality and completeness of OpenStreetMap building footprint data across different regions, with rural areas like Turano having significantly less comprehensive coverage than urban centers like Copenhagen. A secondary factor involves geo-location inaccuracies, particularly in indoor environments where GPS signals may be blocked or where devices rely on lower-accuracy location services.

The high-density classification results reveal another important pattern, with the proportion of points flagged as high-density increasing from 68.04% in Copenhagen to 89.30% in Turano, and even more in other datasets that are that are excluded from this contribution due to space constraints. In

locations where building footprint data is less complete (e.g., Turano), our density-based approach identifies proportionally more privacy-sensitive locations that would otherwise be classified as outdoor and left as non privacy-sensitive data points. This complementary relationship demonstrates the value of implementing multiple, overlapping identification methods for privacy-sensitive data points, particularly in regions with varying data infrastructure quality.

The mobility patterns across datasets show remarkable consistency in the prevalence of stationary measurements (89.47% to 97.90%), revealing the typical usage pattern of portable sensors that are often left in fixed positions for extended periods. However, notable differences emerge in the active movement category, where Gerace shows the highest percentage (4.12%) compared to the minimal active movement in Copenhagen (0.43%) and Turano (0.24%). This variation likely reflects differences in how the individual user operated their device in each location, with Gerace users potentially carrying their device more frequently during walking activities. The higher transit percentage in Gerace (6.40%) compared to other locations further supports this interpretation, suggesting different individual mobility behaviors. It's worth noting that in Copenhagen, where cycling is a dominant transportation mode, some active movement may have been misclassified as transit since typical cycling speeds often exceed the set 15 km/h threshold for transit classification. This highlights the need for location-specific tuning of speed thresholds to account for regional transportation norms, such as Copenhagen's cycling culture versus more pedestrian or motorized transportation in the Italian locations.

Beyond the statistics shown in Table I, it was observed that the administrative boundary enrichment provides effective data anonymization by allowing aggregation at various administrative levels instead of using exact geographical coordinates. For example, measurements can be reported at the municipal level (e.g., Tårnby in Hovedstaden or Gerace in Calabria) while still preserving valuable regional air quality insights. This approach creates a natural privacy-preserving alternative to precise geolocation data, which could potentially hinder participation.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a multi-faceted framework for enhancing both privacy and usability of crowdsourced environmental data is presented. The approach combines spatial density analysis, building boundary detection, mobility pattern recognition, and geographic contextualization to identify and protect privacy-sensitive information while preserving analytical value. By enriching rather than redacting data, the method enables flexible privacy-utility trade-offs that adapt to different geographic contexts and data infrastructure limitations. Testing across diverse locations demonstrated the framework's effectiveness in addressing the inherent challenges of user-driven data collection while transforming privacy-sensitive patterns into valuable research insights without compromising individual privacy.

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